

Supplementary Table S5. List of specimens used to measure whole eye diameter (WED) of left and right eyes (see methods), with family, sampling locality, collection date and depth, registration number, and WED measurements. Abbreviations: NHMUK – Natural History Museum, London, UK; MNHN – Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; UF – Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, USA; ZRC – Zoological Reference Collection, Raffles Museum of Biodiversity Research, National University of Singapore.

Family	Species	Sampling locality	Latitude	Longitude	Collection date	Depth (m)	Registration no.	Right eye WED (µm)	Left eye WED (µm)
Rostellariidae	<i>Rostellariella delicatula</i>	Off Mambare Bay, Papua New Guinea	-7.883333 – -7.866667	148.050000 - 148.016667	08.10.2010	498–501	MNHN-IM-2013- 64480	2163	2176
Rostellariidae	<i>Varicospira cancellata</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.646667	150.736667	23.06.2014	10–15	MNHN-IM-2013- 55221	439	453
Rostellariidae	<i>Varicospira cancellata</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.625	150.775	03.06.2014	–	MNHN-IM-2013- 47468	608	613
Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum delicatum</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.625	150.775	03.06.2014	–	MNHN-IM-2013- 47194	374	410
Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum delicatum</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.625	150.775	03.06.2014	–	MNHN-IM-2013- 47193	417	413
Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum delicatum</i>	Grand Passage, N Province, New Caledonia	-19.83	163.795	28.04.2008	31–36	MNHN-IM-2007- 35460	422	437
Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> B	N Kabanam Point, Papua New Guinea	-5.1	145.803333	17.11.2012	2	MNHN-IM-2013- 13905	441	449
Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> B	N Riwo Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.141667	145.808333	01.12.2012	1–4	MNHN-IM-2013- 17031	550	533

Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> D	S Yabob Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.258333	145.788333	03.12.2012	2–6	MNHN-IM-2013-17611	517	408
Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> D	W Kranket Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.196667	145.82	30.11.2012	23	MNHN-IM-2013-16786	422	439
Seraphsidae	<i>Terebellum terebellum</i> D	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.625	150.775	03.06.2014	–	MNHN-IM-2013-46856	551	545
Strombidae	<i>Aliger gallus</i>	Bay Fort-de-France, Martinique	14.574722	-61.083055	06.10.2016	11–15	MNHN-IM-2013-72989	2438	2304
Strombidae	<i>Barneystrombus kleckhamae</i>	New Ireland, Papua New Guinea	-2.58	150.715	07.09.2014	94–95	MNHN-IM-2013-59098	1044	1015
Strombidae	<i>Canarium erythrinum</i>	In front of Narendry Bay, Madagascar	-14.531667	47.442333	14.07.2009	46–54	MNHN-IM-2007-36698	1055	1063
Strombidae	<i>Conomurex decorus</i>	N Pemba Bay headland, Mozambique	–	–	15.07.2006	–	NHMUK 20060447	1510	1505
Strombidae	<i>Conomurex decorus</i>	Inhaca Is., Maputo Bay, Mozambique	-26.065	32.955	25.11.2011	0–1	MNHN-IM-2013-64494	1695	1614
Strombidae	<i>Conomurex fasciatus</i>	Farasan Is., Abu Lad, Saudi Arabia	16.797667	42.199167	–	–	UF 463647	1037	1065
Strombidae	<i>Conomurex fasciatus</i>	Farasan Is., Abu Lad, Saudi Arabia	16.797667	42.199167	10.03.2013	6–9	UF 463278	1218	1272
Strombidae	<i>Conomurex persicus</i>	Asterias Hotel, Ayia Napa Marina, Cyprus	34.981597	33.953628	26.10.2017	–	NHMUK 20230931	1467	1366
Strombidae	<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.66	150.665	14.06.2014	2–12	MNHN-IM-2013-53759	940	970
Strombidae	<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae</i>	Kranket Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.2	145.813333	22.11.2012	–	MNHN-IM-2013-14905	1075	1023
Strombidae	<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae</i>	Barag Is., Rempy Area, Papua New Guinea	-5.018333	145.798333	15.11.2012	Intertidal	MNHN-IM-2013-13445	2179	1982

Strombidae	<i>Euprotomus bulla</i>	Paquitequete, Pemba, Mozambique	–	–	14.07.2006	–	NHMUK 20060411	1642	2054
Strombidae	<i>Fusistrombus fusiformis</i>	In front of Narendry Bay, Madagascar	-14.531667	47.442333	14.07.2009	46–54	MNHN-IM-2007- 36710	1239	1329
Strombidae	<i>Gibberulus gibberulus</i>	Inhaca Is., Maputo Bay, Mozambique	-26.073333	32.951667	30.11.2011	0–1	MNHN-IM-2013- 64485	1686	1622
Strombidae	<i>Hawaiistrombus scalariforme</i>	Tubuai Is., French Polynesia	-23.425449	-149.426422	24.03.2013	20	MNHN-IM-2013- 48351	343	352
Strombidae	<i>Hawaiistrombus scalariforme</i>	Tubuai Is., French Polynesia	-23.425449	-149.426422	24.03.2013	20	MNHN-IM-2013- 48350	526	508
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus dilatatus</i>	Grand Pass, N Province, New Caledonia	-19.83	163.795	27.04.2008	31–36	MNHN-IM-2007- 34736	1036	1194
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus labiosus</i>	NW Majunga, Madagascar	-15.4	45.933333	12.07.2009	780–1020	MNHN-IM-2007- 36711	1035	992
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus labiosus</i>	Betw. Nosy Be and Nosy Tanikely, Madagascar	–	–	21.05.2008	24–25	UF 423433	1192	1199
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus labiosus</i>	In front of Narendry Bay, Madagascar	-14.536667	47.423333	06.07.2009	50–107	MNHN-IM-2007- 36651	1233	1211
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus labiosus</i>	N Saint-André Cape, Madagascar	-15.791667	44.75	09.07.2009	48	MNHN-IM-2007- 38201	1312	1223
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus robustus</i>	Changi, Singapore	1.3095	103.971167	08.02.2009	–	ZRC MOL.2897	1154	1152
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus robustus</i>	Cyrene Reef, Singapore	–	–	21.06.2012	–	ZRC MOL.14909	1273	1299
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus robustus</i>	E Changi, Singapore	–	–	14.12.2012	–	ZRC MOL.5565	1425	1631
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus turturella</i> B	SW Pulau Semakau, Singapore	1.197633	103.758167	18.02.2009	3	ZRC MOL.2917	1884	1846
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus variabilis</i>	Cyrene Reef, Singapore	–	–	19.08.2012	–	ZRC MOL.3309	1795	1462
Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus vittatus</i>	St John's Is., Singapore	–	–	08.07.2016	–	ZRC MOL.7536	1870	1818

Strombidae	<i>Labiostrombus wienekei</i>	Yomba Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.245	145.788333	06.12.2012	20–25	MNHN-IM-2013-17824	835	822
Strombidae	<i>Lambis lambis</i>	S Dumduman Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.003333	145.793333	09.11.2012	0–1	MNHN-IM-2013-12410	2584	2260
Strombidae	<i>Lambis scorpius</i>	E Sek Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.081667	145.823333	11.12.2012	–	MNHN-IM-2013-18324	1496	1642
Strombidae	<i>Lentigo thersites</i>	Banc Ouest, S Province, New Caledonia	-22.446	166.483	13.11.2017	2–11	UF 510153	2921	3000
Strombidae	<i>Lobatus raninus</i>	Borgnèse Point, Le Marin, Martinique	14.45	-60.896667	09.09.2016	4–8	MNHN-IM-2013-72315	2282	2302
Strombidae	<i>Maculastrombus microunceus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.586667	150.77	02.06.2014	6–22	MNHN-IM-2013-46788	689	686
Strombidae	<i>Maculastrombus microunceus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.628333	150.67	21.06.2014	4–6	MNHN-IM-2013-55168	783	800
Strombidae	<i>Maculastrombus mutabilis</i> B	Monseigneur Beach, S Madagascar	-24.941667	47.118333	27.04.2010-15.05.2010	0–1	MNHN-IM-2009-15843	946	834
Strombidae	<i>Ministrombus minimus</i>	S Yabob Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.258333	145.788333	03.12.2012	2–6	MNHN-IM-2013-17612	790	759
Strombidae	<i>Persististrombus granulatus</i>	Gulf of Panama	–	–	10.04.2004	11–20	UF 372340	1016	1218
Strombidae	<i>Strombus pugilis</i>	E Madame Is., Robert Bay, Martinique	14.671667	-60.88	25.09.2016	1–8	MNHN-IM-2013-71190	1243	1220
Strombidae	<i>Terestrombus terebellatus</i>	Kavieng Lagoon, Papua New Guinea	-2.586667	150.485	16.06.2014	4–16	MNHN-IM-2013-54138	1631	1627
Strombidae	<i>Thetystrombus latus</i>	Anse Bernard, Dakar, Senegal	14.661667	-17.433332	29.08.2009-30.08.2009	0–1	MNHN-IM-2013-50101	1321	1737
Strombidae	<i>Thetystrombus latus</i>	Bay of Goree, Thiwa, Dakar, Senegal	14.611667	-17.448334	03.09.2009	37	MNHN-IM-2013-50048	2027	1884

Strombidae	<i>Tridentarius dentatus</i>	S Kranket Is., Papua New Guinea	-5.205	145.813333	12.11.2012	–	MNHN-IM-2013- 12550	1854	1770
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